

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF CIRCULATION IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS ON THE BASIS OF INDICATIVE EDUCATIONAL MODELS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the pedagogical conditions for improving the system of traction in the training of future specialists based on indicative educational models. In the process of teaching, the importance of the system of tutoring is considered, its impact on the academic and personal development of students, as well as the possibilities of ensuring quality education using modern pedagogical methods. The article will discuss pedagogical conditions, the interaction of teachers and students, as well as the methods and strategies necessary to improve the effectiveness of tyutor's activities.

INTRODUCTION. In the process of training future specialists in the modern educational system, a key place is occupied by the traction system. Tutoring is a system aimed at providing, supporting and developing an individual approach to students in the course of their studies. This article will consider the pedagogical conditions for improving the system of traction on the basis of indicative educational models.

MAIN PART. The Importance of the Tutoring System. The tutoring system plays an important role in increasing student motivation in the reading process, meeting individual needs, and improving reading performance. This system helps students identify their goals, get help in the study process, and find the resources needed for personal development. Tutors play an important role in providing students with support, motivation, and personal development in the course of their studies.

The main tasks of tutoring include Individual support, increasing motivation, improving the training process. To help in accordance with the specific needs of students. To help students develop their abilities and to assist them in setting personal paths. Increase students' interest in reading. To help overcome difficulties in the educational process. To identify problems in the learning process and help solve them. To provide students with the resources they need to make education more efficient. The above-mentioned processes are one of the important tasks of thutorism. The tutoring system is important in helping students achieve their goals, creating relaxation in the study process, and finding the resources necessary for personal development.

Indicative educational models are important tools for managing and controlling pedagogical processes. They are aimed at systematizing the educational processes of students and supporting their development. Indicative models include the following aspects:

Spiritual-aesthetic development: the model of spiritual-aesthetic development is aimed at introducing students to spiritual values and developing their aesthetic feelings. Through an artistic and aesthetic environment, students have the opportunity to express their emotions. Through the formation of mutual respect, cooperation and social relations, the personality and spirituality of students are strengthened.

Creative thought: the purpose of the creative thought model is to encourage students to think innovatively. This model is implemented through the following aspects: teaching students approaches to solving creative problems, helping to develop new ideas, giving students the opportunity to freely express their thoughts through various creative activities (art, design, scientific research), developing projects to implement students' innovative ideas, and forming the basis of the creative idea model by supporting them.

Social activism: the social activism model focuses on teaching students to actively participate in social life. The social activism model is characterized by a number of aspects. Examples of this include giving students a sense of social responsibility, actively participating in society and contributing to solving social problems, teaching students the skills of working in a team, conducting group activities and collaborating.

Indicative educational models are important in supporting the personal and social development of students, enhancing their spiritual and aesthetic abilities, as well as promoting creative thinking and social activity.

It is necessary to create important pedagogical conditions for improving the system of circulation on the basis of indicative educational models. These conditions are aimed at improving the effectiveness of the educational process, strengthening the dialogue between teachers and students, as well as supporting the individual development of students. The following pedagogical conditions are necessary to improve the system of circulation on the basis of indicative educational models:

Teacher Training: Organization of programs for training and development of pedagogical skills for tutors. This ensures that teachers communicate effectively with students.

New pedagogical technologies: application of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process. It allows you to effectively communicate with students and improve their mastering process.

Council and support: advising students on their goals and challenges and creating a system to support them. This contributes to the self-development of students.

Organizational conditions: creation of the necessary organizational conditions for the effective implementation of the system of traction in educational institutions. This ensures effective cooperation between students and faculty.

Monitoring and Evaluation: Implement a monitoring system to assess the effectiveness of the tutoring system. This will allow for continuous review and improvement of pedagogical processes.

It is possible to effectively organize the educational process by creating the necessary pedagogical conditions for improving the system of tutoring on the basis of indicative

educational models. The training of teachers, the application of modern pedagogical technologies, the implementation of a system of student support and monitoring are the main directions of this process. All this will serve to train qualified and competent specialists in the future.

CONCLUSION. Improving the traction system on the basis of indicative educational models will bring the process of training future specialists to a qualitatively new level. This system helps to take into account the individual needs of students, support their development and effectively organize the study process. By creating pedagogical conditions, it will be possible to more successfully implement the tutoring system. This will serve to train qualified and competent specialists in the future.

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